

Identifying Barriers in a Medically Underserved Area

Gabriella Garza, DNP, APRN, FNP-BC -- Deanna Jung DNP, APRN, AGACNP-BC, ACCNS-AG -- Rachel McClanahan, DNP, RN, NCSN

Background

Medically Underserved Populations (MUP)

- Healthy People 2020 calls for equal access to healthcare
- Racially/ethnically diverse
- Lower socioeconomic status
- Increased psychosocial barriers
- Decreased access to healthcare
- High appointment no-show rates
- Poorer health outcomes from chronic diseases like diabetes and heart failure

Problem Statement

Barriers impede patient's healthcare access, health-promoting behavior, and appointment attendance rate.

Purpose

Adapt and implement an evidence-based screening tool, the *Barriers to Health Questionnaire* (BHQ) to:

- Identify prevalent psychosocial barriers to appointment adherence
- Develop targeted interventions to improve resources available in MUPs

Methods

- Convenience sample of current patients
- BHQ was implemented for 14 days
- Descriptive statistics determined the most prominent barriers affecting MUP
- A chi-square analysis to examine if case manager interventions are successful in improving patient adherence to the next scheduled appointment
- IRB approval was obtained through California State University, Fullerton

Nola Pender's Health Promotion Model

Results

- Total patients n=328
- Latino, Hispanic women, 41-55 years of age were the most prominent demographic
- 164 patients were referred to a case manager
- 158 (96%) met with the case manager and had barrier addressed
- Of the 158, 111 (70%) patients adhered to their next scheduled appointment
- A chi-square analysis revealed significantly ($p=.007$) higher attendance at the next scheduled appointment for patients referred to a case manager, compared to patients who were not referred to a case manager

Prevalence of Barriers in a MUP

Discussion

- This project supports the current literature that Hispanic, Latino women predominately have higher rates of psychosocial barriers to healthcare
- Psychosocial barriers affect patient appointment adherence
- Case manager intervention improves patient appointment attendance rates

Implications for Practice

- The BHQ is an effective evidence-based screening tool to identify barriers that negatively impact patient appointment adherence and health outcomes in MUP
- Further research is needed to determine the efficacy of this tool in an effort to alleviate healthcare disparities in MUP
- Case managers are central interventionists that can promote improved health outcomes and appointment adherence in a population at-risk of dying from chronic disease due to a lack of health care access

Conclusion

- Psychosocial barriers may not be easily rectifiable
- Provider screening and case manager intervention is a valuable method to address barriers hindering access to healthcare
- Continued efforts to improve healthcare access in MUPs is vital to advance healthcare and alleviate gaps in care